

Priority Risk Factors Contributing to the Onset of Diabetes Mellitus During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Clinical Evaluation

Ruzimurodov Nodir, Aripova Tamara

Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics of the Academy of Science of the Republic of Uzbekistan., Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Keywords: COVID-19, Diabetes Mellitus, Post-COVID Period, Risk Factors, Metabolic Control, Diabetic Complications.

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has not only brought unprecedented challenges to global health but has also accelerated the onset of various non-communicable diseases, particularly diabetes mellitus (DM). The SARS-CoV-2 virus, responsible for COVID-19, is believed to play a direct role in damaging pancreatic beta cells, thus impairing insulin production and potentially leading to the development of type 2 diabetes. This has been particularly evident in patients recovering from severe cases of COVID-19, where there has been a notable increase in the number of newly diagnosed diabetic patients.

Additionally, the pandemic has placed significant pressure on healthcare systems, leading to disruptions in routine care and metabolic control for pre-existing diabetic patients, causing the disease to progress or decompensate. Patients who already have diabetes and contract COVID-19 often experience more severe symptoms, frequent episodes of decompensation, and complications such as diabetic ketoacidosis and hyperglycemic conditions. Furthermore, unvaccinated individuals show a higher tendency for more severe symptoms and long-term metabolic disturbances post-COVID-19, compared to those who are vaccinated.

Vaccination, while primarily designed to mitigate the severity of COVID-19, has also demonstrated an impact on the clinical progression of diabetes in patients. It is associated with more stable glycemic control and fewer complications. Understanding how these factors interplay with the development and progression of diabetes is crucial for improving prevention strategies and clinical outcomes during pandemics. This study aims to analyze the priority risk factors contributing to the development of diabetes during the pandemic, with particular emphasis on COVID-19 infection and the effects of vaccination.

Objective: The primary objective of this study is to identify and evaluate the key risk factors contributing to the onset and progression of diabetes mellitus during the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing on the role of SARS-CoV-2 infection and the protective impact of vaccination in mitigating disease severity and metabolic disturbances.

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted in the endocrinology department of the Khatyrchinsky Medical District Association from 2022 to 2023. A total of 242 patients were selected using a prospective cohort method. The study population consisted of 138 men and 104 women with an average age of 64.3 ± 2.7 years. Patients were divided into three groups based on their vaccination status and the timing of diabetes onset:

- **Group 1:** 102 unvaccinated patients who developed type 2 diabetes after contracting COVID-19.
- **Group 2:** 53 vaccinated patients who developed type 2 diabetes after recovering from COVID-19.
- **Group 3:** 87 patients with pre-existing type 2 diabetes before contracting COVID-19.

All patients underwent thorough clinical examinations, including a detailed medical history, blood pressure monitoring, BMI calculation, and laboratory tests such as complete blood counts, urine analysis, biochemical blood tests, and coagulograms. Instrumental diagnostics, including X-rays, ultrasound, and electrocardiograms (ECG), were performed to assess cardiovascular and renal function. Glycemic control was measured through fasting blood glucose levels, HbA1c, and insulin sensitivity. The study also monitored complications like diabetic neuropathy, retinopathy, and episodes of ketoacidosis. Data were analyzed to assess the relationship between COVID-19 infection, vaccination status, and the progression of diabetes and its complications.

Results: An analysis of the patients revealed significant differences in symptom severity and complications among the groups. Unvaccinated patients in Group 1 exhibited more severe diabetic symptoms, such as chronic fatigue, polydipsia, polyuria, and frequent episodes of hyperglycemia and decompensation. Complications like neuropathy and retinopathy were prevalent, and the need for hospitalization was more frequent. These patients also reported weight loss and a general deterioration in health, with 90% experiencing pronounced weakness and 85% reporting increased fatigue. Furthermore, these patients had unstable blood sugar levels, leading to frequent hyperglycemic and hypoglycemic episodes.

In contrast, vaccinated patients in Group 2 showed milder symptoms and fewer complications. Hyperglycemia was present but less severe, and symptoms like weight loss and dry mouth were less common. Blood sugar levels were more stable in this group, with fewer episodes of decompensation. These patients also had a lower incidence of neuropathy and retinopathy, and their overall health appeared more stable, with fewer complaints of general weakness and emotional lability. Chronic fatigue was reported in 25% of vaccinated patients, compared to 50% in the unvaccinated group. Complications were less frequent, and the intensity of symptoms was significantly lower.

Patients in Group 3, with pre-existing diabetes, experienced worsening conditions after contracting COVID-19, particularly among those who were not vaccinated. They reported

frequent episodes of hyperglycemia, increased fatigue, and more severe diabetic complications. About 80% of patients in this group experienced general weakness, and 40% reported chronic fatigue. The progression of diabetes-related complications, such as neuropathy and retinopathy, was also more evident in this group.

Conclusion: This study highlights that unvaccinated patients with diabetes who contracted COVID-19 experienced more severe symptoms and complications compared to vaccinated individuals. Vaccination was associated with reduced inflammation, improved metabolic control, and fewer complications. These findings emphasize the importance of vaccination for diabetic patients during the pandemic, not only in preventing severe COVID-19 outcomes but also in stabilizing diabetic conditions and reducing the risk of long-term metabolic disturbances. Effective management of diabetes, particularly in post-COVID-19 patients, should involve vaccination, lifestyle interventions, and routine monitoring to prevent complications and improve health outcomes.